

1 **Beyond Water Quality Assessments in Tropical Rivers:**
2 **Mapping the Water-Energy-Food (WEF)-Nexus Interactions and Community**
3 **Livelihood Dynamics in the Bua River Basin, Malawi.**

4 **SUPPLEMENTARY DATA**

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8 **Figure S1.** Upstream section of the Bua River Basin showing relatively clearer water
9 conditions and reduced turbidity as the river flows through more vegetated and less disturbed
10 catchment areas.

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14 **Figure S2.** Midstream section of the Bua River Basin showing elevated turbidity and
15 suspended sediment loads associated with catchment disturbance, riparian cultivation and
16 runoff-driven sediment mobilization

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18 **Table S1.** Research design for the sampling transects, triplicate seasonal coverage, and GPS-referenced points (station locations) across
 19 the three districts in the Bua River catchment (Source: Author compilation, 2025).

District	Transect point	Location description	Rainy–wet season (Triplicates)	Cold–dry season (Triplicates)	Hot–dry season (Triplicates)	Station name	GPS Coordinates
Mchinji	Point 1	Along the length of the Bua River	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	Kabungwe Area	13.89° S, 33.28° E
	Point 2	3 m away from Point 1 along the length of the river	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	Kabungwe Area	13.89° S, 33.28° E
	Point 3	3 m away from Point 2 along the river channel	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	Kabungwe Area	13.89° S, 33.28° E
	Point 4	Ditches within 300 m radius from the river channel	✓✓✓	—	—	Kabungwe Area	13.89° S, 33.28° E
Dowa	Point 1	Along the length of the Bua River	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	Chika Area	13.28° S, 33.55° E
	Point 2	3 m away from Point 1 along the length of the river	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	Chika Area	13.28° S, 33.55° E
	Point 3	3 m away from Point 2 along the river channel	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	Chika Area	13.28° S, 33.55° E
	Point 4	Ditches within 300 m radius from the river channel	✓✓✓	—	—	Chika Area	13.28° S, 33.55° E
Ntchisi	Point 1	Along the length of the Bua River	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	Chisepo Area	13.09° S, 33.70° E
	Point 2	3 m away from Point 1 along the length of the river	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	Chisepo Area	13.09° S, 33.70° E
	Point 3	3 m away from Point 2 along the river channel	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	Chisepo Area	13.09° S, 33.70° E
	Point 4	Ditches within 300 m radius from the river channel	✓✓✓	—	—	Chisepo Area	13.09° S, 33.70° E

20 Key: GPS coordinates represent central reference points for transect clusters within each district.

21 ✓✓✓ indicates triplicate samples collected per transect per season (n = 3) and “—” indicates no sampling conducted.

Table S2. Major WEF-Nexus interactions identified in the Bua River Basin Nexus

Nexus Interaction	Evidence	Trade-off	Environmental Consequence
Water → Food	Irrigation and riverbank cultivation	Increased crop production	Increased nutrient runoff
Food → Water	Fertiliser application	Food security	Water-quality deterioration
Energy → Water	Charcoal production	Household income	Deforestation and erosion
Water → Energy	River resources support biomass regeneration	Fuel availability	Resource dependence
Food ↔ Energy	Charcoal used to finance agricultural inputs	Income diversification	Increased ecosystem pressure

Table S3. Comparison of community perceptions mapped with observed environmental pressures and supporting physicochemical indicators within the Bua River Basin.

Community perception / reported issue	Observed environmental pressure	Supporting physicochemical indicator(s)	Environmental interpretation
“River water is becoming more turbid and dirtier during rainy periods.”	Riparian cultivation, erosion and sand mining	Elevated turbidity and TSS downstream	Increased sediment transport associated with land disturbance
“Trees along the river are disappearing because of charcoal production.”	Riparian woodland clearance and fuelwood harvesting	Increased turbidity and localised temperature increases	Reduced vegetation buffering and increased runoff exposure
“Water quality has declined near farming areas.”	Agricultural expansion and fertiliser runoff	Elevated ammonia, nitrate and phosphate concentrations	Nutrient enrichment associated with agricultural activities
“Some river sections are becoming shallow and unstable.”	Sand extraction and bank disturbance	Elevated suspended sediments and turbidity	Channel destabilisation and sediment resuspension
“Many households depend directly on the river for washing and bathing.”	Domestic river-use activities	Reduced dissolved oxygen in heavily utilised downstream zones	Localised organic loading and sediment disturbance

“Environmental laws are rarely enforced effectively.”	inadequate governance and monitoring limitations	Basin-wide environmental degradation patterns	Institutional limitations contributing to unsustainable resource use
“Rainfall changes and dry periods are worsening water problems.”	Seasonal hydrological variability and catchment pressure	Seasonal fluctuations in DO, EC and turbidity	Combined effects of climatic and anthropogenic stressors
“Farming near the river has increased because upland soils are less productive.”	Expansion of cultivation into riparian zones	Elevated nutrient concentrations and turbidity	Intensified agricultural encroachment into sensitive areas

Key: DO = Dissolved Oxygen; EC = Electrical Conductivity; TSS = Total Suspended Solids. Community perceptions were obtained through KIIs and FGDs, while environmental observations and physicochemical indicators were derived from field transects and supporting water-quality assessments conducted between June 2022 and June 2024.